

1 **Strong functional stability of soil microbial communities under semiarid Mediterranean**
2 **conditions and subjected to long-term shifts in baseline precipitation**

3

4 Curiel Yuste J^{1,2*}, Fernandez-Gonzalez A.J.³, Fernandez-Lopez M.³, Ogaya, R^{2,4},
5 Penuelas J^{2,4}, Sardans J.^{2,4}, Lloret F.²

6

7 ¹ *Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN), CSIC, Serrano 115 dpdo. E-28006*
8 *Madrid. Spain;* ² *CREAF. E-08193 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), Spain;* ³
9 *Estacion Experimental del Zaidin (EEZ), CSIC, Profesor Albareda, 1. E-18008.*
10 *Granada, Spain,* ⁴ *CSIC. Global Ecology Unit CREAM-CEAB-CSIC-UAB, E-08193*
11 *Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), Spain;*

12

13

14 **Corresponding author:** *Jorge Curiel Yuste; Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales*
15 *(MNCN), Serrano 115 dpdo. E-28006 Madrid. Spain; j.curiel@mncn.csic.es*

16

17

18

19

20

21 **Abstract**

22 We investigated the effect of soil microclimate on the structure and functioning of
23 soil microbial communities in a Mediterranean Holm-oak forest subjected to 10 years of
24 partial rain exclusion manipulations, simulating average drought conditions expected in
25 Mediterranean areas for the following decades. We applied a high throughput DNA
26 pyrosequencing technique coupled to parallel measurements of microbial respiration
27 (R_H) and temperature sensitivity of microbial respiration (Q_{10}). Some consistent changes
28 in the structure of bacterial communities suggest a slow process of community shifts
29 parallel to the trend towards oligotrophy in response to long-term droughts. However,
30 the structure of bacterial communities was mainly determined by short-term
31 environmental fluctuations associated with sampling date (winter, spring and summer)
32 rather than long-term (10 years) shifts in baseline precipitation. Moreover, long-term
33 drought did not exert any chronic effect on the functioning of soil microbial
34 communities (R_H and Q_{10}), emphasizing the functional stability of these communities to
35 this long-term but mild shifts in water availability. We hypothesize that the particular
36 conditions of the Mediterranean climate with strong seasonal shifts in both temperature
37 and soil water availability but also characterized by very extreme environmental
38 conditions during summer, was acting as a strong force in community assembling,
39 selecting phenotypes adapted to the semiarid conditions characterizing Mediterranean
40 ecosystems. Relations of climate with the phylogenetic structure and overall diversity of
41 the communities as well as the distribution of the individual responses of different
42 lineages (genera) to climate confirmed our hypotheses, evidencing communities
43 dominated by thermotolerant and drought-tolerant phenotypes.

44 **Keywords:** Functional stability, CO₂, adaptation, soil bacterial communities,
45 diversity, Mediterranean climate , extreme events

46 **1. Introduction**

47

48 Microorganisms are responsible for at least half of CO₂ emitted by terrestrial
49 ecosystems to the atmosphere (Bond-Lamberty et al., 2004), representing, therefore, a
50 very big source of CO₂ to the atmosphere. Microorganisms are thus key players in
51 maintaining atmospheric gas concentrations and temperatures within acceptable limits
52 for life. They are also primarily responsible for the degradation and detoxification of
53 many environmental pollutants (Lamar and Dietrich, 1990; Aelion and Bradley, 1991),
54 and we are starting to elucidate the functional role of these communities on the
55 dynamics of soil Carbon (C) (e.g. Aerts, 2006; Waldrop and Firestone, 2006; Balsler and
56 Wixon, 2009; Fierer et al., 2007; Curiel Yuste et al., 2010, 2011, Wieder et al. 2013).
57 We further know that microbial diversity is strongly affected by environmental changes,
58 e.g. site productivity (Waldrop et al., 2006), pH (Fierer and Jackson, 2006), plant health
59 and composition (Peay et al., 2010; Curiel Yuste et al., 2012) or drought (Curiel Yuste
60 et al., 2011; Lau and Lennon, 2012). However, the question of whether models should
61 explicitly include microbial diversity to predict ecosystem processes still remains
62 unanswered, given the alleged high functional redundancy of these hyper-diverse
63 communities (Finlay et al., 2004; Allison and Martiny, 2008, Wieder et al. 2013).

64

65 Because climate affects both soil microbial activity (e.g. Rey et al., 2006; Curiel
66 Yuste et al., 2007) and soil microbial community structure (e.g. Zogg et al. 1997; Castro
67 et al. 2010; Curiel Yuste et al. 2011) it is crucial to understand how the ongoing changes
68 in climate may affect the structure and functioning of soil microbial communities.
69 Mediterranean-type ecosystems, where water availability is the most important
70 environmental constraint due to the combination of high summer temperatures and low

71 rainfall (Specht et al.,1983; Larcher, 2000) are expected to be extremely vulnerable to
72 the effects of climate change (Schröter et al., 2005). Global circulation and regional
73 models predict an increase in temperatures in the Mediterranean Basin during the
74 present century, while rainfall is predicted to decrease and become more irregular
75 (Gibelin & Deque, 2003; IPCC, 2007) which makes Mediterranean ecosystems an
76 exceptional playground to test how microbial communities would evolve under more
77 arid conditions.

78

79 Since it is well known that drought strongly limits the physiological performance
80 of microbes and the diffusion of nutrients in the soil pore space (e.g. Davidson and
81 Janssens, 2006; Sardands et al. 2005; 2008), ultimately affecting soil metabolic activity
82 and soil CO₂ emissions (Curiel Yuste et al. 2007; Asensio et al. 2008), it might be
83 expected that the predicted climatic changes might chronically affect the structure and
84 functioning of soil microbial communities. However, the strong functional stability
85 shown by soil microbial communities (Allison and Martiny, 2008, Wieder et al. 2013)
86 which includes the components of resistance (the degree to which a community is
87 insensitive to a disturbance) and resilience (the rate at which a community returns to
88 pre-disturbance conditions) (see Shade et al. 2012) might help counteracting possible
89 climate-driven pressures. A growing body of studies are experimentally evidencing this
90 functional and structural stability against long-term climatic changes (e.g. Williams and
91 Rice 2007; Zul et al. 2007; Cruz-Martinez et al. 2009; Landesman and Dighton 2010;
92 Curiel Yuste et al. 2010; Curiel Yuste et al. 2011). This high functional stability is
93 mainly a cause of the high functional redundancy of these hyper-diverse communities
94 (Schimel 2001), their physiological plasticity to quickly respond to environmental
95 changes (e.g. Placella et al. 2012) and their enormous potential to acquire new genes

96 with respect to other kingdoms (Whittman et al., 1998, Achtman and Wagner 2008)
97 through recombination, mainly in the form of homologous recombination (Fraser et al.
98 2007) or horizontally transfer genes (HGT) (Doolittle and Papke 2006). However, we
99 still need to gather experimental evidences to properly test to what extent soil microbial
100 communities are functionally stable under the adaptive pressures associated with
101 climate-change.

102

103 Here we present the results of a study designed to explore how soil bacterial
104 communities respond to both short-term (three bio-climatically contrasting times of the
105 year) and long-term (10 years of treatment under partial precipitation exclusion)
106 climatic variations. Taxonomic composition and structure of soil bacterial community
107 was studied at a Mediterranean site where experimental precipitation exclusion has
108 reduced soil moisture by up to 25% (10 years average reduction of 13%) with respect to
109 controls during 10 years (Ogaya & Peñuelas, 2007, Ogaya et al., 2011). We used large-
110 scale pyrosequencing of partial 16S rRNA genes to study the structure (taxonomic
111 composition and the relative presence of different taxons within the community) of soil
112 bacterial communities. This technique has recently emerged as a powerful tool that has
113 discovered a vast microbial diversity in soils and a large heterogeneity of microbial
114 communities across biomes (Roesch et al., 2007; Jones et al., 2009; Lauber et al., 2009),
115 land uses (Acosta-Martínez et al., 2008; Will et al., 2010; Nacke, 2011), soil horizons
116 (Will et al., 2010) or forest successional stages (Curiel Yuste et al., 2012). This diversity
117 far exceeded the values obtained using the commonly used fingerprinting techniques,
118 such as terminal restriction fragment length polymorphisms (TRFLP; see. Curiel Yuste
119 et al., 2011). These results were compared with parallel measurements of SOM
120 decomposition and its response to temperature in order to assess the functional

121 performance of the microbial community. The general objectives of this study were to
122 understand how soil microbial communities respond to changes in climate. More in
123 detail our objectives were to assess the degree of structural and functional stability
124 (resistance and/or resilience) of soil microbial communities to environmental changes
125 associated with climatic fluctuations at synoptic time scales (winter, spring and
126 summer) and to long-term shifts in baseline precipitation.

127

128 **2. Materials and Methods**

129

130 **2.1. Experimental site**

131

132 Soil samples were collected from the natural Holm-Oak (*Quercus ilex* L.) forest
133 of the Prades Mountains, located in Southern Catalonia (North-Eastern Iberian
134 Peninsula) (41° 21'N, 1° 2'E, 950m altitude), on a south-facing slope (25%). The soil is
135 a Dystric Cambisol over Paleozoic schist. Its depth ranges between 35 and 100 cm, and
136 Horizon A occupies the 25-30 cm upper layer. The average annual temperature is 12.8°
137 C and the average annual rainfall is 658 mm. Summer drought is pronounced and
138 usually lasts for 3 months. The vegetation is a dense forest dominated by *Quercus ilex*
139 as a dominant tree with abundant presence of *Phillyrea latifolia* L. and *Arbutus unedo*
140 L. and other evergreen species well adapted to drought conditions (*Erica arborea* L.,
141 *Juniperus oxycedrus* L., *Cistus albidus* L.), and occasional individuals of deciduous
142 species (*Sorbus torminalis* (L.) Crantz and *Acer monspessulanum* L.). Eight 15x10 m
143 plots were established at the same altitude (930 m above sea level) along the slope in
144 1999. Four of the plots received the drought treatment and the other four were used as
145 control. The drought treatment consisted of partial throughfall exclusion by suspending

146 PVC strips with wood sticks at a height of 0.5–0.8 m above the soil surface. Strips
147 covered approximately 30% of the total plot surface. Two plastic strips of 14 m long
148 and 1 m wide were placed along the drought treatment plots from the top until the
149 bottom part. A 0.8–1 m deep ditch was excavated along the entire top edge of the upper
150 part of the treatment plots to also intercept runoff water supply. The water intercepted
151 by strips and ditches was conducted outside the plots, below their bottom edge. This
152 drought treatment reduced soil moisture of drought plots by up to 25% (10 years
153 average reduction of 13%) with respect to controls during 10 years, being the reduction
154 larger during wet seasons and lower during dry seasons (Ogaya et al., 2011). For more
155 information about the experimental site, equipment and drought treatment see Ogaya &
156 Peñuelas (2007) and Curiel Yuste et al. (2011).

157

158 ***2.2. Soil organic matter decomposition and temperature sensitivity***

159

160 Soil cores, 4.5 cm diameter and 10 cm depth, were collected using a stainless steel
161 core soil sampler. Samples were collected during three different periods of the year,
162 winter (cold and moist with limited vegetation photosynthetic activity), spring (warm
163 and wet with maximum vegetation photosynthetic activity) and summer (very warm and
164 very dry, with minimum vegetation photosynthetic activity). Three samples were
165 randomly collected within each plot for each date-treatment (winter, spring and summer
166 in control and drought plots). In total 72 soil samples were collected throughout the
167 year, 24 samples per period (three periods), 12 for control and 12 for drought treatment.
168 Each individual soil sample was sieved (2 mm) and analyzed for humidity
169 (gravimetrically), soil organic carbon and microbial biomass (Curiel Yuste et al., 2011).

170 Aliquots (100 g) of each soil sample were stored in plastic jars during 1-2 weeks at
171 room temperature (20-25 °C) prior to measurements of soil CO₂ efflux.

172

173 To assess the temperature sensitivity of soil decomposition, soils were subjected
174 to temperature cycles (Curiel Yuste et al., 2011). Prior to the temperature cycles, sieved
175 soils were maintained at room temperature (aprox. 23 °C) 3 days. Soil moisture at the
176 collection time was kept by maintaining the plastic jars closed during the whole process,
177 avoiding evaporation. During each cycle, respiration rates were measured at three air
178 temperatures (always following the same order): 10, 25, and 45 °C. These soils are
179 normally experiencing these temperatures from winter to summer under field
180 conditions. Incubation temperature was not gradually increased and soil cores went
181 straight from one temperature to the other. Soil CO₂ efflux from the soil samples was
182 measured at each of the three temperatures 24 hours after the given temperature was
183 applied. Thirty minutes prior to measurement jars were opened to equilibrate the air
184 CO₂ concentrations of the jar and the room. After the 30 minutes we used a modified
185 soil chamber connected to an EGM-4 portable system (PP-systems, UK) to measure soil
186 CO₂ efflux. Commercial soil chamber of PP-systems, the SRC-1, was enlarged with a 1
187 l, 13 cm large PVC tube of the same diameter as the SRC-1 chamber and with a rubber
188 rim at the end. Plastic jars containing the incubated soils were then introduced into the
189 enlarged chamber, sealing the inner volume as a closed system. The modified chamber
190 produced readings similar to those obtained with the commercial SRC-1 (Curiel Yuste
191 et al. 2011, Asensio et al. 2012). The obtained CO₂ effluxes were then the soil microbial
192 respiration.

193

194 In addition we used the decomposition rates obtained at each of the incubation
195 temperatures to assess the relative increase in soil decomposition with temperature. Q_{10}
196 computes the relative increase in decomposition rate per 10 °C difference.

197

$$198 \quad R_H = BS_{10} * Q_{10}^{(T-10/10)} \quad \text{equation 1}$$

199

200 Where R_H is the measured soil CO₂ efflux, BS_{10} is the basal respiration rate at 10
201 °C, Q_{10} is the relative change in R_H with 10 °C increases and T is the temperature of soil
202 at measurement time. We fitted this exponential function for each of the six soils
203 studied. We then explored the effect of sampling-date and treatment over R_H and Q_{10}
204 using Analysis of Variance (ANOVAS). We applied these analyses to R_H at different
205 temperatures (10, 25 and 45 °C), R_H averaged across the temperature range ($Av R_H$) and
206 Q_{10} . We first studied possible differences in R_H and Q_{10} associated with sampling-date
207 for each individual treatment (control and drought). We then studied differences in R_H
208 and Q_{10} associated with treatment for each individual sampling date (winter spring and
209 summer).

210

211 ***2.3. DNA amplification and Pyrosequencing***

212

213 Soil DNA was extracted from each individual soil sample using the PowerSoil™
214 DNA Isolation Kit (MoBio, Laboratories Inc., CA), following the manufacturer's
215 recommendations. Briefly, the DNA extraction methods involved chemical lysis of
216 microbial cells with gentle bead-beating. Released DNA was bound to a silica spin filter
217 which was subsequently washed, and the DNA was recovered in an elution buffer

218 solution. DNA yields and quality were checked after electrophoresis in 0.8% (w/v)
219 agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide under UV light (Sambrook et al., 1989).

220

221 Partial bacterial 16S rRNA gene sequences were obtained from the analysis of
222 each individual sample using the coded-primer approach to multiplex pyrosequencing
223 (Binladen *et al.*, 2007). PCR amplification of the hypervariable V4-V5 region of the
224 16S rRNA gene was performed above each individual soil DNA extraction. PCR was
225 performed with the 8 bp key-tagged universal primers U519F and U926R (Baker *et al.*,
226 2003). To reduce artifacts associated with PCR, such as chimeras, we adjusted the
227 amplification process following Acinas et al., (2005) modified protocol, consisting on
228 reducing the number of PCR cycles to only 25. We further adjusted the protocol to
229 Roche's recommendations in order to further diminish the occurrence of artifacts. The
230 PCR mixtures (25 μ l) contained 25 pmol of each primer, 1.8 mM MgCl₂, 0.2 mM
231 dNTPs, 1 x the corresponding Taq buffer, 1 U of Taq Master (5 Prime, USA) and 10 ng
232 of the same DNA template used above. The PCR program consisted of an initial
233 denaturation step at 94°C for 4 min, 25 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 15 seconds,
234 primer annealing at 55°C for 45 seconds and extension at 72°C for 1 minute, followed
235 by a final step of heating at 72°C for 10 minutes. For each sample, amplicons were
236 generated in three replicate PCRs.

237

238 Amplicons of the same treatment (control and drought) x date (winter, spring and
239 summer) combination were then pooled in equimolar amounts in six composite samples
240 and subjected to pyrosequencing with the Genome Sequencer Titanium FLX system
241 (454| Life Sciences, Branford, CT, USA) at Life Sequencing S.L. (Valencia, Spain).
242 Sequences were excluded from the analysis following four criteria: 1- if the length read

243 was less than 150 bp; 2- if the forward primer sequences contained more than two
244 errors; 3- if the sequences had 1 or more Ns; and, 4- if the quality index, according to
245 the .qual file generated during the pyrosequencing process, was less than 20. The partial
246 16S rRNA sequences obtained from each sample are reported as “trimmed” in Table 1.
247 5. We checked filtered sequences for chimeras using the UCHIME algorithm (Edgar et
248 al., 2011).

249

250 ***2.4. Taxonomic assignment of sequence reads and structural community indexes***

251

252 Trimmed sequences were processed through the Ribosomal Database Project
253 (RDP) pyrosequencing pipeline (<http://pyro.cme.msu.edu>) release 10 (Cole et al., 2009).
254 To avoid bias in the interpretation of the data all six samples were rarefied to the
255 composite sample with the lowest number of sequences (7779 Sequences of the winter
256 control). Thus, 7779 sequences were chosen at random from the pool of sequences
257 obtained for the other 5 composite samples. The qualified sequences were clustered into
258 Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs), defined on the basis of a distance of 3%, by
259 complete linkage clustering, and were assigned to phyla by the RDP-II classifier, using
260 an 80% confidence threshold (Wang et al., 2007). Sequences that could not be classified
261 to a phylum at this level of confidence were excluded from subsequent phylum
262 composition analyses

263

264 Each unique sequence was further aligned using the RDP pyrosequencing
265 function aligner to generate phylogenetically ordered rRNA sequences (Nawrocki &
266 Eddy, 2007). Aligned data sets were clustered using the default parameters for the RDP
267 Clustering function. The resulting clusters were used to calculate the Shannon-Weaver

268 (H') index and the respective evenness, the Chao1 estimator, and the rarefaction curves,
269 using the pyrosequencing analysis tools from RDP at the level of 3% dissimilarity,
270 which was considered to approximately correspond with species level.

271

272 With the same clusters file above described we extracted one sequence for each
273 cluster at 3% (Operational Transcriptomic Unit, OTU), obtaining a representative
274 sequence for each OTU. Then, we aligned the representatives' sequences with RDP
275 Aligner Tool. With the aligned data we built a Lower Triangular Formatted Distance
276 Matrix from RDP's Pyrosequencing Pipeline. At the end, we used the tool Excel from
277 Microsoft Office 2010 to view the Matrix and extract the average value of Phylogenetic
278 Distances (Mean Phylogenetic Distance; MPD) and standard deviation. This is a
279 measure of the phylogenetic structure of the communities used to evaluate, among other
280 things, the degree of functional specialization (phylogenetically clustered communities)
281 versus functional diversification (phylogenetically distant communities) (e.g. Verdú and
282 Pausas, 2007; Pausas and Verdú, 2008).

283

284 ***2.5. Statistical analysis of pyrosequencing data***

285

286 The RDP sample abundance statistics tool was used to calculate the Jaccard's
287 index to compare the six composite samples (Chao et al., 2006). Aligned data sets from
288 each sample were merged into a single cluster file, which was used to construct a
289 distance matrix at 3% dissimilarity, which produced a dendrogram using the
290 unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA). We further applied an
291 analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA, mothur, v. 1.21.0) to obtain significant
292 differences between the overall studied communities (10,000 iterations). This method is

293 widely used in population genetics to test the hypothesis that genetic diversity within
294 two populations is not significantly different from that which would result from pooling
295 the two populations (e.g. Excoffier et al., 1992; Curiel Yuste et al. 2012). Although our
296 analysis does not allow account for variability between plots, this approach permits the
297 statistical comparisons at our site level between microbial communities submitted to the
298 drought treatment in the three considered sampling dates. We further applied the
299 Unweighted Unifrac algorithm (Lozupone and Knight, 2005) to further explore
300 differences in phylogenetic diversity among samples (10,000 iterations).

301

302 Taxonomic composition and structure of the soil microbial community was
303 further analysed by comparing the effect of treatment and date over the members of the
304 community. Libraries generated from each date- treatment combinations (6 total) were
305 then compared pair-wise by estimating the likelihood that the frequency of membership
306 of a given taxon (i.e. phylum, class, order) is the same for the different libraries (in our
307 case, the six combinations of treatment and date) (Cole et al., 2007; 2009). This is a
308 methodology extensively used to detect variations in the abundance of a given bacterial
309 lineages among samples (e.g. Cole et al., 2007; 2009; Curiel Yuste et al. 2012; Torres-
310 Cortes et al. 2012).

311

312 ***2.6. Response of bacterial lineages and diversity to environmental variables***

313

314 We profited from the long time series of environmental data collection in these
315 experimental plots (see Ogaya et al. 2011), to obtain data on soil temperature and foliar
316 Fv/Fm, which is a measurement ratio that represents the maximum potential quantum
317 efficiency of Photosystem II and could be used as a proxy for plant physiological

318 activity. Moisture averages per date-treatment combinations were obtained from the data
319 set of Curiel Yuste et al., (2011), whereas data on temperature and foliar Fv/Fm was
320 obtained from the results shown in Ogaya et al., (2011). We, therefore, explored the
321 possible effects on the structural characteristics of soil bacterial communities (richness,
322 diversity, MPD and equitability) and the absolute abundance of all bacterial genera
323 (N=6) of the variations across dates (winter, spring and summer) and treatments (control
324 and drought) of the different environmental (soil temperature, moisture) and plant
325 physiological (foliar Fv/Fm) explicative variables.

326

327 We applied a non-parametric test (U de Mann Whitney) under the null hypothesis
328 that the response of soil bacterial communities under two contrasting environmental
329 ranges (e.g. low versus high temperatures) are the same against an alternative
330 hypothesis, especially that the response of these communities for this particular
331 environmental range differs. To do that we arbitrarily defined a threshold for each of
332 the three environmental/physiological variables (foliar Fv/Fm, soil temperature and soil
333 moisture) to split the total population (N = 6 soil microbial communities) in two equally
334 represented halves of 3 microbial communities. For instance, the 6 different bacterial
335 communities were split in communities sampled under wet condition (SWC >13%) and
336 under dry conditions (SWC < 13%). The Mann Whitney U test was then applied under
337 the null hypotheses (H_0) that the average relative abundances of both populations will
338 not be significantly different. From all Mann Whitney U tests performed we obtained a
339 standardized U coefficient (z) assuming that the U coefficients generated by the
340 statistical package for each individual Mann-Whitney test were normally distributed.
341 The magnitude and sign of z reflects the response of a given genus to a given
342 environmental factor and can, therefore, be used as a proxy of the functional response of

343 each individual genus to a given environmental/physiological variable. For instance,
344 when the abundance of a given genus was consistently higher under, e.g. high levels of
345 soil moisture (meaning that this genus respond positively to increasing soil water
346 availability), z would be highly positive (close to 2). On the contrary, when the
347 abundance of a genus was consistently higher under lower soil moistures z would be
348 highly negative (close to -2). Finally, in between the two extremes a continuum
349 spectrum conformed by z (low or no significant) that accounts for genera not
350 significantly sensitive to this particular environmental variable. Then, we explored the
351 distribution of z 's to evaluate the ecological response of the community as a whole. For
352 this purpose, we evaluated the skeweness of the distributions of z for a given
353 environmental/physiological variable under the assumption that a distribution
354 significantly skewed towards negative or positive values, and hence significantly
355 deviated from normality, would mean that more genera within the community were
356 adapted to a given ecological condition (negative or positive response to an
357 environmental/physiological variable) with respect to the other condition.

358

359 Prior to this, and given that data was collected in three consecutive times of the
360 year (winter, spring and summer) we also applied non-parametric statistics to test for
361 possible temporal autocorrelation (repeated measures) and/or for correlations between
362 explicative variables (Fv/Fm, soil moisture and soil temperature) and sampling-date. To
363 do that, we applied a Generalized Linear Model approach designed as follows. We
364 defined an ordinal response using bacterial abundance (all genera, all sampling date-
365 treatments) as the response variable with two fixed factors (sampling-date and
366 treatment) and a covariate (Fv/Fm, soil moisture or soil temperature). We check the
367 significance of the principal effects of the explicative variables (Wald Chi-square). If

368 the effect of the covariate variable (Fv/Fm, soil moisture or soil temperature) was
369 significant, it was assumed that the environmental variable had an effect over the
370 observed variations in bacterial relative abundances despite the inherent effect of time
371 (sampling-date). Results suggest that there was a significant effect of the environment
372 (soil moisture (SWC) and plant Fv/Fm) independent from the inherent effect associated
373 with sampling date (Table S1). We, therefore, assumed that there was a time-
374 independent effect of the environment over the observed variability of bacterial
375 abundances.

376

377 **3. Results**

378

379 Pyrosequencing-based analyses and subsequent statistical inference produced
380 from 7779 to 14089 prokaryotic sequences per date-treatment (Table 1). Sequences
381 clustered in operational taxonomic units (OTUs, after rarefying all samples to the
382 composite sample with the lowest number of sequences, 7779) on the basis of a 3%
383 taxonomic distance yielded values from 1728 up to 2424 OTUs (Table 1). The Chao-1
384 index show richness values from 2822 (Spring control) up to 7197 different OTU's
385 (Winter drought), while the Shannon-Weaver index (H) yielded diversity values from
386 6.54 (Spring control) up to 7.05 (Winter drought) (Table 1). Mean phylogenetic distance
387 of the community was lowest in winter samples and highest during summer (Table 1).

388

389 Regarding changes in taxonomic composition of soil bacterial communities, the
390 analyses of similarity with the abundance statistics tool and the analysis of molecular
391 variance (AMOVA) and unweighted UNIFRAC indicates that both treatment and date
392 exerted a significant ($p < 0.0001$) effect on soil bacterial community structure. The

393 analysis of similarity from AMOVA further indicates that bacterial communities from
394 the six different treatment-date combinations were significantly different from each
395 other. Distances obtained with the Jaccard index (Figure 1) and the temporal
396 fluctuations in the relative contribution to the community of the main bacteria phyla
397 (Figure 2) indicated, however, that the effect of sampling date on the bacterial
398 community composition was stronger than the effect of the 10 years-long drought
399 treatment.

400

401 The distribution of the different taxa is represented in Figure 2. Proteobacteria
402 was the most represented phylum in all the samples (30% of the total bacterial
403 population on average), followed by Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Acidobacteria.
404 Those four phyla comprised 80% of the total bacterial population. Gemmatidomonas
405 Planctomycetes, Verrucomicrobia, Chloroflexibacterias and Firmicutes were less well
406 represented. Distribution of the main bacterial phyla shows important temporal
407 fluctuations in the relative contribution, but small or marginal fluctuations with respect
408 to treatment (Figure 2). Indeed, pairwise comparisons of bacterial communities show
409 that under both control and drought treatments the presence of Proteobacteria in summer
410 soils was low with respect to winter and spring, the presence of Actinobacteria in spring
411 soils was low with respect to winter and summer soils while Bacteroidetes peaked
412 significantly in spring and Firmicutes in summer (Figures 3a and 3b). Under drought
413 treatment a peak in presence of Acidobacteria was observed in spring (Figure 3b).

414

415 Pairwise comparison of bacterial communities of the two treatments indicates
416 significant effect of long-term drought in the relative abundance of some of the most
417 representative bacterial taxa (Figure 3c). Proteobacteria was the only phylum

418 consistently better represented in control soils throughout the year with respect to
419 drought-treatment soils, while Acidobacteria was the only phylum consistently better
420 represented in soils under long-term drought with respect to control (Figure 3c). There
421 were also changes in some taxa for date-treatment combinations: Actinobacteria
422 appeared underrepresented in drought soils during winter and spring, but during
423 summer the trend was inverted (Figure 3c); Bacteroidetes and Verrucomicrobia were
424 better represented in control than in drought soils in summer communities while
425 Gemmatimonadetes were better represented in drought soils during the same period
426 (Figure 3c).

427

428 Figure 4 shows average values of soil moisture (Figure 4a), soil microbial
429 respiration (Figure 4b) and temperature sensitivity of SOM (Figure 4c) averaged per
430 date-treatment. Rates of microbial respiration at different temperatures (10, 25 and 45
431 °C), averaged for the whole temperature range ($A_v R_H$) and Q_{10} are shown in Table S2.
432 Spring coincided with the highest values of soil metabolic activity (R_H and BS_{10}) and
433 soil moisture (SWC) (Figure 4a and 4b, Table S2), as well as with the lowest values of
434 sensitivity of soil microbial respiration to temperature (Q_{10}) (Figure 4c, Table S2).
435 Overall, sampling date exerted a stronger effect than treatment over both R_H (at
436 different temperatures and averaged) and Q_{10} (Figure 4 and 5; Table S3). ANOVA
437 confirmed that sampling-date exerted a significant effect over R_H (at each sampling
438 temperature and averaged across temperatures) and over Q_{10} under both control and
439 partial rain exclusion (drought) treatments (Figure 4; Table S3). ANOVA's also showed
440 that drought treatment exerted a significant negative effect over R_H (at different
441 temperatures and averaged across temperatures) during winter and summer, when soil
442 moisture values were also significantly lower under partial rain exclusion treatments

443 (Figure 4a and 4b, Table S3). However, the similarity of soil moistures in control and
444 drought treatments during the spring sampling-date (Figure 4a) caused by a previous-
445 day extreme rain event (>100 mm), coincided with a leveling of the rates of soil
446 microbial respiration at both treatments (Figure 4b, Table S3). On the other hand, Q_{10}
447 was only significantly affected by partial water exclusion during summer, when
448 moistures reached their lowest values (Figure 4a and 4c; Tables S2 and S3). Finally, we
449 observed that rates of soil microbial respiration averaged across temperatures at both
450 treatments were equally and positively affected by soil moisture (Figure 5).

451

452 Our results also show that both the diversity and the phylogenetic structure of the
453 bacterial communities were strongly affected by climate-related variables (Table 2,
454 Figure 6). Bacterial diversity (H') was strongly affected by soil moisture (Figure 6a)
455 while average phylogenetic distance of the different bacterial communities across date-
456 treatment combinations were mainly affected by temperature (Figure 6b).

457

458 We further show the distribution of U standardized coefficients (z) from the
459 relation of each individual genera with foliar Fv/Fm (Figure 7a), soil moisture (Figure
460 7b) and soil temperature (Figure 7c). Distribution of the coefficients was never normal
461 for the three different environmental/physiological variables (K-S <0,0001) (Figure 7).
462 Response of bacterial genera to foliar Fv/Fm and temperature were piled-up at the right
463 of the distribution (negative skewness) (Figures 7a and 7c) and to the left with soil
464 moisture (positive skewness) (Figures 7b). This skewness resulted in averaged z
465 significantly different from zero for the three different environmental/physiological
466 variables (Figure 7). The averaged response of bacterial abundances with foliar Fv/Fm
467 or temperature were significantly positive ($0,22 \pm 0,06$ and $0,24 \pm 0,06$ respectively; see

468 Figures 7a and 7c) whereas the averaged response to soil moisture was significantly
469 negative ($-0,32 \pm 0,05$; Figure 7b).

470

471 **4. Discussion**

472

473 We here show that variability of both structural (Figures 1, 2 and 3) and
474 functional (Figure 4 and 5; table S1) properties of soil microbial communities were
475 determined to a big extent by shorter-term but intense environmental changes and to a
476 lesser extent by longer-term (10-years shifts in baseline precipitation) but mild
477 environmental changes. This prevalence of the short-term over the longer-term effects
478 in microbial communities is something that has been repeatedly observed (Williams and
479 Rice 2007; Zul et al. 2007; Cruz-Martinez et al. 2009; Landesman and Dighton 2010;
480 Curiel Yuste et al. 2011) and respond to the distinct magnitude of changes in moisture
481 and temperature associated with treatment (mild) with regard to sampling-date (intense;
482 see Ogaya et al. 2011). Nonetheless, some consistent changes in the taxonomic
483 composition of the bacterial community associated with long-term partial water
484 exclusion, such as the increase in relative abundance of Proteobacteria and
485 Acidobacteria in the control and treatment plots, respectively (Figures 2 and 3c), was
486 indicative of a slow structural transformation of these communities in response to this
487 mild, but also prolonged, drought. In particular the predominance under drought
488 treatment of Acidobacteria over Proteobacteria, which has been attributed to relatively
489 more oligotrophic (Smit et al. 2001, Castro et al. 2010, Fierer et al. 2007; Yergeau et al.
490 2011) and low-pH niches (Lauber et al. 2009; Foesel et al. 2013), was in consonance
491 with the slow but consistent process towards more oligotrophic soils induced by the
492 effect of prolonged and accentuated droughts over the stoichiometry of plant tissue and

493 litter (Sardans et al. 2008) and enzyme activity, resulting in slower nutrient turnover
494 (Sardans 2005, 2010). We cannot discern, however, the causal-effect relations between
495 those structural changes in the communities of these soils subjected to long-term
496 drought and the observed trends towards more oligotrophic conditions. Future studies
497 should, therefore, be designed to deepen in the causal-effect relations behind the
498 observed parallel evolution of the structure of the microbial communities and the
499 stoichiometry of these soils.

500

501 Despite those structural changes associated with long-term drought, we could not
502 find evidences of chronic effects on the functioning of the communities (Figures 4 and
503 5). Similarly to what we observed for the structure of bacterial communities, the
504 functioning of soil microbial communities was more influenced by short-term-driven
505 environmental changes than by long-term shifts in baseline precipitation (Figure 4 and 5
506 Table S2 and S3). This prevalence of the short- but intense (sampling date effect) over
507 the long- but mild (10 years precipitation exclusion) effects further agreed with
508 observations trends in enzyme activity (Sardans and Peñuelas 2005, Sardans and
509 Peñuelas 2010) or soil respiration (Asensio et al. 2008) and confirms that the
510 functioning of those communities was mainly limited by low accessibility to water (low
511 soil moisture) with no evidences of a chronic decrease in the potential capacity of soil
512 microbial communities to decompose SOM caused by long-term drought. In fact, the
513 observed physiological resilience and resistance observed in this study (Figures 4 and 5)
514 are compelling evidences of the functional stability of these communities subjected to
515 fluctuating environmental conditions at different time-scales (environmental changes
516 associated with sampling date versus long-term changes in baseline climatic
517 conditions). During winter and summer rates of R_H were negatively affected by the

518 lower soil moistures under precipitation exclusion plots (Figure 4). However the
519 absence of differences in soil microbial respiration (R_H) when soil moisture was equated
520 in all plots, due to a previous-day extreme rain event during the spring-time sampling
521 date (Figure 4a and 4b), and the similar relation of soil moisture with R_H in control and
522 drought soils (Figure 5), suggests that the metabolic capacity of these communities was
523 only limited by access to water, being functionally resilient to this long-term shift in
524 baseline precipitation. Besides the observed resilience of the microbial respiration, the
525 lack of differences in the temperature sensitivity of soil microbial respiration (Q_{10}),
526 which is a coefficient very sensitive to changes in water and nutrient/substrate
527 accessibility (Davidson and Janssens 2006), was a strong indication of the strong
528 physiological resistance of these communities to drought. this Q_{10} coefficient only
529 exhibited some sensitivity to drought under the extreme limitations in water imposed
530 by the partial exclusion during the summer (Figure 4a and 4b).

531

532 We therefore hypothesize that the particular conditions of the Mediterranean
533 climate may have historically favored phenotypes that could tolerate the strong seasonal
534 shifts in both temperature and soil water availability but also the extreme environmental
535 conditions characterizing Mediterranean ecosystems during summer (high temperatures
536 and prolonged droughts). In the particular case of bacterial communities, the
537 combination of an historical process of natural selection of genotypes more suitable for
538 the semi-arid conditions of the Mediterranean systems (e.g. Waldrop and Firestone
539 2006a,b; Cruz-Martinez et al. 2009) together with the capacity of these communities to
540 change in response to changing environments (Whittman et al., 1998, Achtman and
541 Wagner 2008), due to their short generation times and strong potential to acquire
542 genetic diversity (Fraser et al. 2007; Doolittle and Papke 2006) may have helped

543 compensating for long-term (decadal) perturbation-driven changes in environmental
544 conditions.

545

546 A number of evidences support this hypothesis. For instance, the drop in bacterial
547 richness and diversity during spring (the period of maximal soil moisture, R_H and plant
548 photosynthetic activity) (Table 1, Figure 6) confirms that less taxa dominated over the
549 entire bacterial community under optimal conditions whereas during summer, and under
550 the year-lowest soil moistures, bacterial communities were richer and more diverse
551 (Table 1, Figure 6). The Mann Whitney U test further confirmed that bacterial
552 communities were more phylogenetically diverse (higher average phylogenetic
553 distance) and taxonomically diverse (higher values of Shannon-Weaver diversity index)
554 under drier and warmer conditions, respectively (Figure 6, Table 2). These results
555 altogether suggest that the sub-optimal microclimatic conditions of summer favored a
556 community more diverse and more phylogenetically distant than the microclimatic
557 conditions of other periods of the year. The skewed distributions of z from the relation
558 of temperature and moisture with the different genera (Figure 7) confirmed that overall
559 these bacterial communities had a net thermo- and drought-tolerant profile.

560

561 The strong skeweness (towards positive values) of the distribution of coefficients
562 points, therefore, to a community favoring thermotolerant (lineage showing a consistent
563 positive response to temperature) over psychrotolerant (lineage showing a consistent
564 negative response to temperature) phenotypes (Figure 7c). Psychrotolerance is a
565 lifestyle that depends on complex interactions among different set of genes and it
566 implies additive changes in overall aminoacid composition of proteins and several
567 phenotypic changes (Methe et al., 2005; Margesin et al., 2007) which might not be

568 competitive in a system where soil temperatures are generally mild for most of the year.
569 On the other hand, the observed negative correlation between moisture and diversity
570 (Figure 7b) resulted in quite a contra-intuitive finding, given the strong dependence of
571 most prokaryotes on the aquatic environment (Whittman et al., 1998), as reflected in a
572 strong positive relation between moisture and microbial biomass (e.g. Wardle et al.,
573 1992) and/or microbial-mediated processes such as SOM decomposition (e.g. Rey et al.,
574 2006; Curiel Yuste et al., 2007). In this study soil microbial respiration was also
575 positively affected by soil moisture (Figure 5), but the distribution of coefficients from
576 the relation of soil moisture with the absolute abundance of the different genus
577 conforming the community suggest that the environmental conditions were favoring
578 drought-tolerant phenotypes (Figure 7b), which further agrees with the observed low
579 impact of long-term water exclusion in the functioning of these communities.

580

581 **Conclusions**

582

583 We here show that long-term shifts in baseline precipitation, simulating future
584 scenarios in the Mediterranean basin as those predicted by GCM's, had a moderate
585 effect over the structure and functioning of soil microbial communities. We found that
586 these microbial communities showed strong structural and functional stability facing
587 environmental transformations lasting for years. These results are, therefore, of interest
588 to understand to what extent climate-driven changes in the composition of microbial
589 communities can be compensated by their functional resilience/resistance (Allison and
590 Martiny 2008). We therefore conclude that climate trend to aridity, itself, will hardly be
591 sufficient to explain permanent cumulative transformations in the ecology of soil
592 microbial communities, at least for those occurring in Mediterranean basin soils and at

593 decadal time-scales. Other indirect effects, such as drought-induced slowing of C and
594 nutrient cycles (Sardans et al 2007, 2008) or increase in tree defoliation and mortality
595 (Carnicer et al. 2011), and its effect on the structure and functioning of these
596 communities (Curiel Yuste et al. 2012), may have, therefore, even more impact on the
597 ecology of these communities than direct climatic effects.

598

599 **Acknowledgements**

600

601 The authors are indebted to the Spanish government projects CONSOLIDER INGENIO
602 MONTES (CSD2008-00040), SECASOL (CGL2009-08101), DRIM (CGL2010-
603 16373), and GLOVOCS (CGL2010-17172), the Catalanian government projects 2009
604 SGR 247 and 458 and Junta de Andalucía government Proyecto de Excelencia P08-
605 CVI-03549. JCY wants to thank Laura Barrios Alvarez (Area de Informática Científica
606 del CSIC) for her scientific advice during the writing of this article. AJFG received a
607 predoctoral fellowship (FPU) from the Spanish Ministry of Education.

608

609

610

611 **Bibliography**

- 612 Acosta-Martinez, V., Dowd, S., Sun, Y., Allen, V., 2008. Tag-encoded pyrosequencing
613 analysis of bacterial diversity in a single soil type as affected by management and
614 land use. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 40, 2762-2770.
- 615 Achtman, M., Wagner, M., 2008. Microbial diversity and the genetic nature of
616 microbial species. *Nat Rev Micro* 6, 431-440.
- 617 Aelion, C.M., Bradley, P.M., 1991. Aerobic biodegradation potential of subsurface
618 microorganisms from a jet fuel-contaminated aquifer. *Applied and Environmental*
619 *Microbiology* 57, 57-63.
- 620 Aerts, R., 2006. The freezer defrosting: global warming and litter decomposition rates
621 in cold biomes. *Journal of Ecology* 94, 713-724.
- 622 Allison, S.D., Martiny, J.B.H., 2008. Resistance, resilience, and redundancy in
623 microbial communities. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the*
624 *United States of America* 105, 11512-11519.
- 625 Asensio, D., Penuelas, J., Ogaya, R., Llusia, J., 2007. Seasonal soil and leaf CO₂
626 exchange rates in a Mediterranean holm oak forest and their responses to drought
627 conditions. *Atmospheric Environment* 41, 2447-2455.
- 628 Balsler, T.C., Wixon, D.L., 2009. Investigating biological control over soil carbon
629 temperature sensitivity. *Global Change Biology* 15, 2935-2949.
- 630 Battistuzzi, F.U., Feijao, A., Hedges, S.B., 2004. A genomic timescale of prokaryote
631 evolution: insights into the origin of methanogenesis, phototrophy, and the
632 colonization of land. *Bmc Evolutionary Biology* 4.
- 633 Beer, C., Reichstein, M., Tomelleri, E., Ciais, P., Jung, M., Carvalhais, N., Roedenbeck,
634 C., Arain, M.A., Baldocchi, D., Bonan, G.B., Bondeau, A., Cescatti, A., Lasslop,
635 G., Lindroth, A., Lomas, M., Luysaert, S., Margolis, H., Oleson, K.W., Rouspard,
636 O., Veenendaal, E., Viovy, N., Williams, C., Woodward, F.I., Papale, D.,
637 Terrestrial Gross Carbon Dioxide Uptake: Global Distribution and Covariation with
638 Climate. *Science* 329, 834-838.
- 639 Bond-Lamberty, B., Wang, C.K., Gower, S.T., 2004. A global relationship between the
640 heterotrophic and autotrophic components of soil respiration? *Global Change*
641 *Biology* 10, 1756-1766.
- 642 Brooks, D.R., McLennan, D.A., 1991. Phylogeny, ecology, and behaviour: a research
643 program in comparative biology, *Phylogeny, ecology, and behaviour: a research*
644 *program in comparative biology.*, pp. i-xii, 1-434.
- 645 Bryant, J.A., Lamanna, C., Morlon, H., Kerkhoff, A.J., Enquist, B.J., Green, J.L., 2008.
646 Microbes on mountainsides: Contrasting elevational patterns of bacterial and plant
647 diversity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of*
648 *America* 105, 11505-11511.
- 649 Castro, H.F., Classen, A.T., Austin, E.E., Norby, R.J., Schadt, C.W., Soil Microbial
650 Community Responses to Multiple Experimental Climate Change Drivers. *Applied*
651 *and Environmental Microbiology* 76, 999-1007.
- 652 Cavalier-Smith, T., 2002. The neomuran origin of archaeobacteria, the negibacterial root
653 of the universal tree and bacterial megaclassification. *International Journal of*
654 *Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* 52, 7-76.
- 655 Chao, A., Chazdon, R.L., Colwell, R.K., Shen, T.-J., 2006. Abundance-based similarity
656 indices and their estimation when there are unseen species in samples. *Biometrics*
657 62, 361-371.

658 Chazdon, R.L., 2003. Tropical forest recovery: legacies of human impact and natural
659 disturbances. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology Evolution and Systematics* 6, 51-71.

660 Cole, J.R., Chai, B., Farris, R.J., Wang, Q., Kulam-Syed-Mohideen, A.S., McGarrell,
661 D.M., Bandela, A.M., Cardenas, E., Garrity, G.M., Tiedje, J.M., 2007. The
662 ribosomal database project (RDP-II): introducing myRDP space and quality
663 controlled public data. *Nucleic Acids Research* 35, D169-D172.

664 Cole, J.R., Wang, Q., Cardenas, E., Fish, J., Chai, B., Farris, R.J., Kulam-Syed-
665 Mohideen, A.S., McGarrell, D.M., Marsh, T., Garrity, G.M., Tiedje, J.M., 2009.
666 The Ribosomal Database Project: improved alignments and new tools for rRNA
667 analysis. *Nucleic Acids Research* 37, D141-D145.

668 Cruz-Martínez, K., Suttle, B.K., Brodie, E.L., Power, M.E., Andersen, G.L., Banfield,
669 J.F., 2009. Despite strong seasonal responses, soil microbial consortia are more
670 resilient to long-term changes in rainfall than overlying grassland. *ISME Journal*, 3:
671 738-744

672 Curiel Yuste, J., Ma, S., Baldocchi, D.D., 2010. Plant-soil interactions and acclimation
673 to temperature of microbial-mediated soil respiration may affect predictions of soil
674 CO₂ efflux. *Biogeochemistry* 98, 127-138.

675 Curiel Yuste, J.C., Baldocchi, D.D., Gershenson, A., Goldstein, A., Misson, L., Wong,
676 S., 2007. Microbial soil respiration and its dependency on carbon inputs, soil
677 temperature and moisture. *Global Change Biology* 13, 2018-2035.

678 Curiel Yuste, J.C., Penuelas, J., Estiarte, M., Garcia-Mas, J., Mattana, S., Ogaya, R.,
679 Pujol, M., Sardans, J., 2011. Drought-resistant fungi control soil organic matter
680 decomposition and its response to temperature. *Global Change Biology* 17, 1475-
681 1486.

682 Curiel Yuste J., Barba J., Fernandez-Gonzalez M., Fernandez-Lopez A.J., Mattana, S.,
683 Martinez-Vilalta J., Nolis, P., Lloret, F., 2012. Changes in soil bacterial community
684 triggered by drought-induced gap succession preceded changes in soil C stocks and
685 quality. *Ecology and Evolution* 2, 3016-3031.

686 Davidson, E.A., Janssens, I.A., 2006. Temperature sensitivity of soil carbon
687 decomposition and feedbacks to climate change. *Nature* 440, 165-173.

688 Denef, K., Six, J., Paustian, K., Merckx, R., 2001. Importance of macroaggregate
689 dynamics in controlling soil carbon stabilization: short-term effects of physical
690 disturbance induced by dry-wet cycles. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 33, 2145-
691 2153.

692 Doolittle, W.F., Papke, R.T., 2006. Genomics and the bacterial species problem.
693 *Genome Biology* 7, 116.

694 Dworkin, J., Losick, R., 2005. Developmental commitment in a bacterium. *Cell* 121,
695 401-409.

696 Edgar, R.C., Haas, B.J., Clemente, J.C., Quince, C., Knight, R., UCHIME improves
697 sensitivity and speed of chimera detection. *Bioinformatics* 27, 2194-2200.

698 Excoffier, L., Smouse, P.E., Quattro, J.M., 1992. Analysis of molecular variance
699 inferred from metric distances among dna haplotypes - application to human
700 mitochondrial-dna restriction data. *Genetics* 131, 479-491.

701 Fierer, N., Bradford, M.A., Jackson, R.B., 2007. Toward an ecological classification of
702 soil bacteria. *Ecology* 88, 1354-1364.

703 Fierer, N., Jackson, R.B., 2006. The diversity and biogeography of soil bacterial
704 communities. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United*
705 *States of America* 103, 626-631.

- 706 Finlay, B.J., Maberly, S.C., Cooper, J.I., 1997. Microbial diversity and ecosystem
707 function. *Oikos* 80, 209-213.
- 708 Flynn, D.F.B., Mirotnick, N., Jain, M., Palmer, M.I., Naeem, S., 2011. Functional and
709 phylogenetic diversity as predictors of biodiversity-ecosystem-function
710 relationships. *Ecology* 92, 1573-1581.
- 711 Foessel, B.U., Nägele, V., Naether, A., Wüst, P.K., Weinert, J., Bonkowski, M., Lohaus,
712 G., Polle, A., Alt, F., Oelmann, Y., Fischer, M., Friedrich, M.W., Overmann, J.,
713 2013. Determinants of Acidobacteria activity inferred from the relative abundances
714 of 16S rRNA transcripts in German grassland and forest soils. *Environmental*
715 *Microbiology*, n/a-n/a. Fraser, C., Hanage, W.P., Spratt, B.G., Recombination and
716 the Nature of Bacterial Speciation. *Science* 315, 476-480.
- 717 Gibelin, A.L., Deque, M., 2003. Anthropogenic climate change over the Mediterranean
718 region simulated by a global variable resolution model. *Climate Dynamics* 20, 327-
719 339.
- 720 Gupta, R.S., Origin of diderm (Gram-negative) bacteria: antibiotic selection pressure
721 rather than endosymbiosis likely led to the evolution of bacterial cells with two
722 membranes. *Antonie Van Leeuwenhoek International Journal of General and*
723 *Molecular Microbiology* 100, 171-182.
- 724 Harvey, P.H., Pagel, M.D., 1989. Comparative studies in evolutionary ecology: using
725 the data base, *Toward a more exact ecology.*, pp. 209-227.
- 726 Hogberg, P., Nordgren, A., Buchmann, N., Taylor, A.F.S., Ekblad, A., Hogberg, M.N.,
727 Nyberg, G., Ottosson-Lofvenius, M., Read, D.J., 2001. Large-scale forest girdling
728 shows that current photosynthesis drives soil respiration. *Nature* 411, 789-792.
- 729 IPCC (2007) *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of*
730 *Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel*
731 *on Climate Change [Solomon, S., D. Qin, M. Manning, Z. Chen, M. Marquis, K.B.*
732 *Averyt, M.Tignor and H.L. Miller (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge,*
733 *United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA.*
- 734 Janssens, I.A., Lankreijer, H., Matteucci, G., Kowalski, A.S., Buchmann, N., Epron, D.,
735 Pilegaard, K., Kutsch, W., Longdoz, B., Grunwald, T., Montagnani, L., Dore, S.,
736 Rebmann, C., Moors, E.J., Grelle, A., Rannik, U., Morgenstern, K., Oltchev, S.,
737 Clement, R., Gudmundsson, J., Minerbi, S., Berbigier, P., Ibrom, A., Moncrieff, J.,
738 Aubinet, M., Bernhofer, C., Jensen, N.O., Vesala, T., Granier, A., Schulze, E.D.,
739 Lindroth, A., Dolman, A.J., Jarvis, P.G., Ceulemans, R., Valentini, R., 2001.
740 Productivity overshadows temperature in determining soil and ecosystem
741 respiration across European forests. *Global Change Biology* 7, 269-278.
- 742 Jones, R.T., Robeson, M.S., Lauber, C.L., Hamady, M., Knight, R., Fierer, N., 2009. A
743 comprehensive survey of soil acidobacterial diversity using pyrosequencing and
744 clone library analyses. *Isme Journal* 3, 442-453.
- 745 Kembel, S.W., Cahill, J.F., Jr., Independent Evolution of Leaf and Root Traits within
746 and among Temperate Grassland Plant Communities. *Plos One* 6.
- 747 Lamar, R.T., Dietrich, D.M., 1990. Insitu depletion of pentachlorophenol from
748 contaminated soil by phanerochaete spp. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*
749 56, 3093-3100.
- 750 Landesman, W.J., Dighton, J., 2010. Response of soil microbial communities and the
751 production of plant-available nitrogen to a two-year rainfall manipulation in the
752 New Jersey Pinelands. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 42, 1751-1758.
- 753 Larcher, W., 2000. Temperature stress and survival ability of Mediterranean
754 sclerophyllous plants. *Plant Biosystems* 134, 279-295.

755 Lau, J.A., Lennon, J.T., Rapid responses of soil microorganisms improve plant fitness
756 in novel environments. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the*
757 *United States of America* 109, 14058-14062.

758 Lauber, C.L., Hamady, M., Knight, R., Fierer, N., 2009. Pyrosequencing-Based
759 Assessment of Soil pH as a Predictor of Soil Bacterial Community Structure at the
760 Continental Scale. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 75, 5111-5120.

761 Lozupone, C., Knight, R., 2005. UniFrac: a new phylogenetic method for comparing
762 microbial communities. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 71, 8228-8235.

763 Margesin, R., Neuner, G., Storey, K.B., 2007. Cold-loving microbes, plants, and
764 animals-fundamental and applied aspects. *Naturwissenschaften* 94, 77-99.

765 Methe, B.A., Nelson, K.E., Deming, J.W., Momen, B., Melamud, E., Zhang, X.J.,
766 Moul, J., Madupu, R., Nelson, W.C., Dodson, R.J., Brinkac, L.M., Daugherty,
767 S.C., Durkin, A.S., DeBoy, R.T., Kolonay, J.F., Sullivan, S.A., Zhou, L.W.,
768 Davidsen, T.M., Wu, M., Huston, A.L., Lewis, M., Weaver, B., Weidman, J.F.,
769 Khouri, H., Utterback, T.R., Feldblyum, T.V., Fraser, C.M., 2005. The
770 psychrophilic lifestyle as revealed by the genome sequence of *Colwellia*
771 *psychrerythraea* 34H through genomic and proteomic analyses. *Proceedings of the*
772 *National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 102, 10913-10918.

773 Misson, L., Gershenson, A., Tang, J.W., McKay, M., Cheng, W.X., Goldstein, A., 2006.
774 Influences of canopy photosynthesis and summer rain pulses on root dynamics and
775 soil respiration in a young ponderosa pine forest. *Tree Physiology* 26, 833-844.

776 Nacke, H., Thuermer, A., Wollherr, A., Will, C., Hodac, L., Herold, N., Schoening, I.,
777 Schrupf, M., Daniel, R., Pyrosequencing-Based Assessment of Bacterial
778 Community Structure Along Different Management Types in German Forest and
779 Grassland Soils. *Plos One* 6.

780 Nawrocki, E.P., Eddy, S.R., 2007. Query-dependent banding (QDB) for faster RNA
781 similarity searches. *Plos Computational Biology* 3, 540-554.

782 Ogaya, R., Penuelas, J., 2007. Tree growth, mortality, and above-ground biomass
783 accumulation in a holm oak forest under a five-year experimental field drought.
784 *Plant Ecology* 189, 291-299.

785 Ogaya, R., Penuelas, J., Asensio, D., Llusia, J., 2011. Chlorophyll fluorescence
786 responses to temperature and water availability in two co-dominant Mediterranean
787 shrub and tree species in a long-term field experiment simulating climate change.
788 *Environmental and Experimental Botany* 71, 123-127.

789 Pausas J.G., Verdú M., 2008. Fire reduces morphospace occupation in plant
790 communities. *Ecology* 89, 2181-2186.

791 Peay, K.G., Kennedy, P.G., Davies, S.J., Tan, S., Bruns, T.D., Potential link between
792 plant and fungal distributions in a dipterocarp rainforest: community and
793 phylogenetic structure of tropical ectomycorrhizal fungi across a plant and soil
794 ecotone. *New Phytologist* 185, 529-542.

795 Raich, J.W., Potter, C.S., 1995. Global patterns of carbon-dioxide emissions from soils.
796 *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 9, 23-36.

797 Reichstein, M., Tenhunen, J.D., Roupsard, O., Ourcival, J.M., Rambal, S., Dore, S.,
798 Valentini, R., 2002. Ecosystem respiration in two Mediterranean evergreen Holm
799 Oak forests: drought effects and decomposition dynamics. *Functional Ecology* 16,
800 27-39.

801 Rey, A., Jarvis, P., 2006. Modelling the effect of temperature on carbon mineralization
802 rates across a network of European forest sites (FORCAST). *Global Change*
803 *Biology* 12, 1894-1908.

804 Roesch, L.F., Fulthorpe, R.R., Riva, A., Casella, G., Hadwin, A.K.M., Kent, A.D.,
805 Daroub, S.H., Camargo, F.A.O., Farmerie, W.G., Triplett, E.W., 2007.
806 Pyrosequencing enumerates and contrasts soil microbial diversity. *Isme Journal* 1,
807 283-290.

808 Sambrook, J., Fritsch, E. F. , Maniatis, T., 1989. *Molecular cloning, a laboratory*
809 *manual*, 2nd ed , Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor, NY,
810 Sect 6 1-6 19

811 Sardans, J., Penuelas, J., 2005. Drought decreases soil enzyme activity in a
812 Mediterranean *Quercus ilex* L. forest. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 37, 455-461.

813 Sardans, J., Penuelas, J., Ogaya, R., 2008. Experimental drought reduced acid and
814 alkaline phosphatase activity and increased organic extractable P in soil in a
815 *Quercus ilex* Mediterranean forest. *European Journal of Soil Biology* 44, 509-520.

816 Sardans, J., Peñuelas, J., 2010. Soil Enzyme Activity in a Mediterranean Forest after Six
817 Years of Drought. *Soil Science Society of American Journal* 74, 838-851.

818 Schroter, D., Cramer, W., Leemans, R., Prentice, I.C., Araujo, M.B., Arnell, N.W.,
819 Bondeau, A., Bugmann, H., Carter, T.R., Gracia, C.A., de la Vega-Leinert, A.C.,
820 Erhard, M., Ewert, F., Glendining, M., House, J.I., Kankaanpaa, S., Klein, R.J.T.,
821 Lavorel, S., Lindner, M., Metzger, M.J., Meyer, J., Mitchell, T.D., Reginster, I.,
822 Rounsevell, M., Sabate, S., Sitch, S., Smith, B., Smith, J., Smith, P., Sykes, M.T.,
823 Thonicke, K., Thuiller, W., Tuck, G., Zaehle, S., Zierl, B., 2005. Ecosystem service
824 supply and vulnerability to global change in Europe. *Science* 310, 1333-1337.

825 Schimel, J.P., 2001. Biogeochemical models: implicit vs. explicit microbiology. In:
826 *Global Biogeochemical Cycles in the Climate System*. E.D. Schulze, S.P. Harrison,
827 M. Heimann, E.A. Holland J.J. Lloyd, I.C. Prentice, and D. Schimel (Eds).
828 Academic Press. Pp. 177-183.

829 Shade, A., Peter, H., Allison, S.D., Baho, D., Berga, M., Buergermann, H., Huber, D.H.,
830 Langenheder, S., Lennon, J.T., Martiny, J.B.H., Matulich, K.L., Schmidt, T.M.,
831 Handelsman, J., 2012. Fundamentals of microbial community resistance and
832 resilience. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 3.

833 Six, J., Conant, R.T., Paul, E.A., Paustian, K., 2002. Stabilization mechanisms of soil
834 organic matter: Implications for C-saturation of soils. *Plant and Soil* 241, 155-176.

835 Smit, E., Leeftang, P., Gommans, S., van den Broek, J., van Mil, S., Wernars, K., 2001.
836 Diversity and seasonal fluctuations of the dominant members of the bacterial soil
837 community in a wheat field as determined by cultivation and molecular methods.
838 *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 67, 2284-2291.

839 Specht, R.L., Moll, E.J., 1983. Mediterranean-type heathlands and sclerophyllous
840 shrublands of the world - an overview. *Ecological Studies* 43, 41-65.

841 Srivastava, D.S., Cadotte, M.W., MacDonald, A.A.M., Marushia, R.G., Mirotnick,
842 N., Phylogenetic diversity and the functioning of ecosystems. *Ecology Letters* 15,
843 637-648.

844 Swenson, N.G., Enquist, B.J., 2007. Ecological and evolutionary determinants of a key
845 plant functional trait: Wood density and its community-wide variation across
846 latitude and elevation. *American Journal of Botany* 94, 451-459.

847 Torres-Cortés, G., Millán, V., Fernández-González, A.J., et al., 2012. Bacterial
848 community in the rhizosphere of a cactus species during dry and rainy seasons
849 assessed by deep sequencing. *Plant and Soil* 357, 275-288

850 Verdu, M., Pausas, J.G., 2007. Fire drives phylogenetic clustering in Mediterranean
851 Basin woody plant communities. *Journal of Ecology* 95, 1316-1323.

852 Waldrop, M.P., Firestone, M.K., 2006. Response of microbial community composition
853 and function to soil climate change. *Microbial Ecology* 52, 716-724.

854 Waldrop, M.P., Zak, D.R., Blackwood, C.B., Curtis, C.D., Tilman, D., 2006. Resource
855 availability controls fungal diversity across a plant diversity gradient. *Ecology*
856 *Letters* 9, 1127-1135.

857 Wang, Q., Garrity, G.M., Tiedje, J.M., Cole, J.R., 2007. Naive Bayesian classifier for
858 rapid assignment of rRNA sequences into the new bacterial taxonomy. *Applied and*
859 *Environmental Microbiology* 73, 5261-5267.

860 Wardle, D.A., 1992. A comparative-assessment of factors which influence microbial
861 biomass carbon and nitrogen levels in soil. *Biological Reviews of the Cambridge*
862 *Philosophical Society* 67, 321-358.

863 Whitman, W.B., Coleman, D.C., Wiebe, W.J., 1998. Prokaryotes: The unseen majority.
864 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*
865 95, 6578-6583.

866 Wieder, W.R., Bonan, G.B., Allison, S.D., 2013. Global soil carbon projections are
867 improved by modelling microbial processes. *Nature Clim. Change* advance online
868 publication.

869 Will, C., Thuermer, A., Wollherr, A., Nacke, H., Herold, N., Schrumpf, M., Gutknecht,
870 J., Wubet, T., Buscot, F., Daniel, R., Horizon-Specific Bacterial Community
871 Composition of German Grassland Soils, as Revealed by Pyrosequencing-Based
872 Analysis of 16S rRNA Genes. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 76, 6751-
873 6759.

874 Williams, M.A., Rice, C.W., 2007. Seven years of enhanced water availability
875 influences the physiological, structural, and functional attributes of a soil microbial
876 community. *Applied Soil Ecology* 35, 535-545.

877 Xu, L.K., Baldocchi, D.D., Tang, J.W., 2004. How soil moisture, rain pulses, and
878 growth alter the response of ecosystem respiration to temperature. *Global*
879 *Biogeochemical Cycles* 18.

880 Yarza, P., Richter, M., Peplies J.R., Euzéby, J., Amann, R., Schleifer, K.H., Ludwig,
881 W., Glöckner, F.O. et al., 2008. The All-Species Living Tree project: A 16S rRNA-
882 based phylogenetic tree of all sequenced type strains. *Systematic and Applied*
883 *Microbiology* 31: 241–250.

884 Yergeau, E., Bokhorst, S., Kang, S., Zhou, J., Greer, C.W., Aerts, R., Kowalchuk, G.A.,
885 Shifts in soil microorganisms in response to warming are consistent across a range
886 of Antarctic environments. *ISME J* 6, 692-702.

887 Zul, D., Denzel, S., Kotz, A., Overmann, J.r., 2007. Effects of Plant Biomass, Plant
888 Diversity, and Water Content on Bacterial Communities in Soil Lysimeters:
889 Implications for the Determinants of Bacterial Diversity. *Applied and*
890 *Environmental Microbiology* 73, 6916-6929.

891

892

Figure captions

Figure 1. Cladogram of the six different soil bacterial communities based on Jaccard distance (3% dissimilarity). All bacterial communities were different among each other according to the analyses of molecular variance (AMOVA) and unweighed Unifrac algorithm. Ctrl W= Control winter; DR W= drought winter; Ctrl Sp= Control spring; DR Sp= drought spring; Ctrl Su= Control summer; DR Su= drought summer

Figure 2. Relative abundance of the most representative soil bacterial phyla/classes (Proteobacteria is presented at the class level) for the three different seasons under study: Winter (W), Spring (Sp) and Summer (Su).

Figure 3. Differences in the relative abundance (with respect to average relative abundance) of the most representative soil bacterial phyla in relation to sampling date in: (a) control treatment and (b) drought treatment; and (c) differences in relative abundance of control and drought treatments per sampling date, where positive values represent more abundance in ctrl with respect to drought plots, and negative more abundance in drought with respect to ctrl soils. Taxa were arranged in panels according to their relative abundance. In (a) and (b) different letters indicate significant differences between microhabitats at the 0.001 p-level using the approach reported in Cole et al. (2007, 2009). In (c) asterisks indicate significant differences between treatments (control and drought) at the 0.001 p-level using the approach reported in Cole et al. (2007, 2009). Prot = Proteobacteria; Act = Actinobacteria; Bact = Bacteroidetes; Acid = Acidobacteria; Gem = Gemmatimonas; Verr = Verrucomicrobia; Firm = Firmicutes; Planc = Planctomyces.

Figure 4. Average (n=12) soil moisture (4a), SOM decomposition (R_H ; 4b) and Q_{10} of the SOM decomposition (4c) averaged per treatment and sampling date. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean. Asterisks designated significant differences (<0,05) between treatments.

Figure 5. Linear relations between averaged soil moisture and R_H for control plots (solid symbols) and treatment plots (open symbols). Error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 6. Relations between: (a) soil moisture (SWC) and bacterial diversity (Shannon-Weaver index); and (b) air temperature and mean phylogenetic distance (MPD). Cief. stand. = standardized coefficient from the Mann Whitney U tests.

Figure 7. Distribution of the standardized coefficients from the Mann Whitney U tests applied between the absolute abundance of different bacterial lineages (genus level) and Fv/Fm (7a); soil moisture (7b) and soil temperature (7c). Asterisks in "Av." (Average standardized coefficient of the correlation for the whole community, N =300) represent values significantly different from 0 (at 0,05 probability, T-test).